

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF COVID-19 POSITIVITY DURING ITS FIRST AND SECOND WAVE AMONGST DIFFERENT AGE AND GENDER GROUPS OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

An epidemiological survey was conducted to identify a worldwide contagious disease of (SARS)-CoV-2 (COVID-19) acute respiratory syndrome. It is considered as extremely infectious disease and mostly spread between people through respiratory droplets by coughs and sneezes. It was 1st transmitted to humans in Wuhan, China and became the 1st source of infection among human to human in community transfer. Coronavirus disease outbreak was first announced as public health emergency on 30th January 2020 by World Health Organization (WHO). Rate of occurrence of COVID-19 varies according to season among different age and gender groups. Incident of effected COVID-19 patients are observed higher in 1st wave than 2nd wave in Pakistan. Study samples of COVID-19 data were collected from sample management department of a well-known private lab in Lahore. The result showed that proportion of effected persons with COVID-19 during 1st wave has a higher ratio of positive reported cases as compared to 2nd wave of COVID-19.

KEY WORDS: Coronavirus, Pathogenicity, public health, epidemic, 1st and 2nd wave virulence.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 is one of several contagious emerging infectious disease outbreaks in recent times with considerable public health and economic effects. A coronavirus attains its name from the way it appears under a microscope. The name corona is derived from Latin word meaning “crown” or “wreath”. Generally, the round virus has a “crown” shape of proteins known as peplomers extending out from its center in all direction under a microscope. Coronaviruses linked to the subfamily named Coronavirinae in the specific family called Coronaviridae. Coronaviruses (COVID-19) are specific group of enveloped viruses with single-stranded non-segmented and positive-sense containing RNA genomes (Chen *et al.* 2020). There are several types of human coronaviruses vary in

severity. Doctors currently discovered seven kinds of coronavirus that can infect the human's beings. Important strains that infect more acute complications viral include MERS-CoV, which induce Middle East respiratory syndrome (Silva-Cayetano *et al.*) This has preceded to the development of PCR based specific polymerase chain reaction diagnostic tests for the detection of new infection in many different countries (Corman *et al.* 2020). SARS-CoV-2, previously indicated as an unidentified beta-coronavirus, is the coronavirus of seventh member of family which infects human beings, different from both strains MERS-CoV and as well as SARS CoV, SARS-CoV-2 (Zhu *et al.* 2020b). The outbreak is possibly related to the sale of bush meat derived from wild or captive

sources in the sea food market of Wuhan, China (Adachi *et al.* 2020).

In structure, Coronaviruses are positively stranded RNA viruses in shape. Its genome is packed within the nucleocapsid (N) protein and surrounded by the membrane (M) protein, envelope (E) protein, and the spike (S) protein. Generally, the projection of the spike on the virus surface modifies the crown appearance of corona virus. The spike protein (S Protein) performs most important function in cell attachment and antigenic recognition (Shereen *et al.* 2020). It also plays crucial role in viral fusion and antibody neutralization induction. The membrane protein (M) is the most plentiful in the envelope and it portrays a key role in the assembly of the virion. It also cooperates with other structural proteins (N, S, and E). The protein (N) is an extremely basic phosphoprotein that merges with RNA to produce the helical nucleocapsid. It also cooperates with protein M, and it is enveloped by a lipid bilayer in which the envelope proteins (M, S and E) are embedded. This protein is participated in the activities that are associated to the viral genome. It also plays role in virus replication cycle (Zhang *et al.* 2020). The envelope (E) protein is smallest in structural proteins and plays role in the production and maturation of the virus. The inner side of the virion is a vacuum, separating the central core from the envelope was examined using Cryo-electron microscopy. These cores are founded by the genomic RNA associated with the N nucleoprotein. The single strand of viral RNA has positive polarity. It is one of the largest RNA viral genome and size range is 27.6 to 31.5 kb (Walls *et al.* 2020).

The first two cases of COVID-19 were confirmed on 26th February 2020 by the Government of Pakistan. These two cases were verified from Karachi and Islamabad and they were pilgrims, came back from Iran. Symptoms vary from one person to another person with coronavirus (COVID-19). It may give rare or no symptoms. However, it can also start to acute disease and may be destructive. Common symptoms at the onset of disease were cough, Fever and Breathlessness. It may take two to fourteen days for a person to shown symptoms after viral infection. The Reverse transcriptase PCR is used for detection of RNA. This quantitative test has been commonly used for the detection and pathogenic diagnostics of COVID-19. Other diagnostic techniques for COVID-19 comprises on chest X-Rays and CT scans. These detection techniques expose the presence of virus in patients with negative RT-PCR results even with the occurrence of the symptoms related with the viral

disease. COVID-19 is recent epidemic in Pakistan as much has been described on disease etiology and epidemiology genomics and biology characteristics. Rate of occurrence of COVID-19 varies according to season among different age and gender groups. Another research was conducted to evaluate the impacts of travel limitations on the progress of corona virus in the central Europe, Spain and the France. The results concluded that the unrestrained travel has increased the dissemination of Covid-19 (Linka *et al.* 2020). A study revealed the biological and epidemiological patterns in the incidence and fatality due to the outbreak of Covid-19. This viral infection has raised threat globally. Many research centers like World Health Organization and Center of Disease Control and Prevention have provided the data of Covid-19 cases. Due to the present condition of increasing infections, health institutes have introduced preventive measures like social distancing, good hygiene's, travel limitations and health medications may help us in managing the spread of Corona virus (Meo *et al.* 2020).

Another cross-sectional study was directed to explain the relationship of Covid-19 mortality with many factors like demographic, quarantine, examining health parameters and wearing face masks. In conclusion, significant results were obtained, indicating that individuals who are following the guidelines have negatively linked with the Corona virus fatality rate as compared to those who are not following considerations (Leffler *et al.* 2020).

In 2002 to 2012, simultaneously, 2 most pathogenic COVID-19 viruses with the zoonotic origination, (SARS-CoV) severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus and (MERS-CoV) Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus), originate in human beings and occurred fatal respiratory disease, making in 21st century originating coronaviruses (COVID-19) a new public health concern (Cui *et al.* 2019). It has overwhelmingly surpassed SARS- (severe acute respiratory syndrome) and MERS- (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) in terms of these two numbers of diseased persons and the contagious criteria of epidemic areas. The present outbreak of coronavirus (COVID-19) has an alarming situation to global public health (Deng and Peng 2020). At the eighth December 2019 according to studies first confirmed case originated (Wu and McGoogan 2020). Huang *et al.* (2020) stated the immunological state of 41 patients which were infected by SARS CoV-2. Among these 13 patients were included in ICU and 28 non-ICU cases for survey. They observed that the patients infected

with SARS-CoV-2 had higher amounts of IFN- γ , IL1B, IP10, and MCP1. They also indicated that this possibly proceeded to the activation of T-helper-1 (Th1) cell responses. Moreover, they stated that the ICU cases had higher concentrations of IP10, GCSF, MCP1, MIP1A, and TNF α as compared to non-ICU cases. To be concluded, cytokine storm was associated with the severity of disease in patients (Huang et al. 2020).

Lin et al., (2020) reported that the patients of COVID-19 showed symptoms of diarrhea, abdominal pain, anorexia, and nausea. When ACE2 receptor expressed in the intestine tract, there becomes very high possibility that virus route for attack in the gastrointestinal tract. By employing RT-PCR, the viral RNA was found in the esophagus, stomach, duodenum, and rectum specimens of severely affected patients. However, viral RNA specimen on the duodenum was found only one of the four non severe affected patients (Bijnen et al. 2018).

Ding et al. (2003) carried out an autopsy survey and they reported that 2 patients infected with COVID family virus demonstrated edema across the small veins of brain. In addition, the also examined slight edema in tissues of brain with demyelination of certain nerve fibers and some focal neural degeneration (Ding et al. 2003). The Reverse transcriptase PCR is used for detection of RNA. The RNA is reverse transcribed to DNA source and so on. This quantitative test has been commonly used for the detection and pathogenic diagnostics of COVID-19. Since the beginning of the disease, WHO has issued a protocol established by the Pasteur Institute of Paris (Corman et al. 2020) that designate a set of primers that target distinct regions of the SARS-CoV-2 genome for diagnostic analysis.

Other diagnostic techniques for COVID-19 comprises on chest X-Rays and CT scans. These detection techniques expose the presence of virus in patients with negative RT-PCR results even with the occurrence of the symptoms related with the viral disease. The chest CT scan is more effective technique than chest X-ray for the initial exposure of the disease. This specialized imaging analysis utilizes X-rays to generate 3D images of the chest for better understanding of infection (Hosseiny et al. 2020). A

unique procedure based on the quadruplex assay for the identification of SARS-CoV-2 infection seemed to be a valuable diagnostic tool for variance diagnosis. By using this objective, one-step quadruplex real-time reverse transcription PCR (rRT-PCR) assay was experimented by Ni et al., (2020) for simultaneous detection. It also targeted differentiation among ORF1ab and N genes of SARS-CoV-2, influenza A virus (hIAV) and influenza B virus (hIBV). The experimental result depicted that Correlation coefficients (R²) and amplification efficiencies (E) of all single plex and multiplex (rRT-PCR) reactions falls within the acceptable range (Ni et al. 2020)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research study is conducted in a Private Lab (Chughtai Labs) Lahore. Work was performed on COVID-19 patient data of 1st and 2nd wave in different age and gender groups of Pakistan.

DATA COLLECTION

Samples statistical data of COVID-19 were received from molecular department and sample nature was nasopharyngeal swabs collected which were 9 months data from May 2020 to February 2021. The data was categorized in month wise May 2020 to September 2020 as 1st Wave and October 2020 to February 2021 as 2nd wave.

REAL TIME PCR

Polymerase chain reaction consists of three steps Denaturation, Annealing and Extension. Rotor-Gene Q instrument is constructed to perform Real Time PCR and end point thermal cycling by using polymerase chain reaction in molecular biology applications.

PREPARING PCR MASTER MIX

All components were thawed before use following recipe followed for making PCR reaction mix. This recipe is for one sample it will multiply with sample number using for PCR reaction. Master Mix for more than 5 samples reaction mix 10% extra added.

RECIPE FOR PCR PREPARATION

Serial No	Components	Quantity(μ L)
1	PCR reaction Mixture	15
2	Internal control	0.2
3	Sample	10

4	Positive/negative control	10
5	Total volume	25

AMPLIFICATION

The extracted RNA was amplified on QIAGEN Rotor Gene Q-3000 by using Bosphore® novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) detection kit v2 is based on Real Time PCR method. Which target region (orf1ab) amplified and by using fam filter fluorescence detection is accomplished. Screening region of 2019-nCoV (E region) is amplified and by using cy5 filter fluorescence

detection is Accomplished which detect coronavirus that includes 2019-nCoV, and bat SARS like corona viruses under the subgenus serbeco virus. Bosphore® novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) detection kit used thermal protocol composed of reverse transcription step. The thermal protocol steps indicated below

THERMAL CONDITIONS FOR PCR

PCR Steps	Temperature (°C)	Time (min)
Reverse Transcription	50°C	17:00min
Initial denaturation	95°C	06:00min
Denaturation	97°C	00:03min
Annealing	60°C	00:03min
(Data collection)		
Hold	32°C	02:00min

STATISTICAL DATA ANALYSIS

Collected data of each month of 1st wave and 2nd wave of COVID-19 data was grouped into 3 groups according to age one was ≤30 years, group 2nd was 31-60 years and group 3rd was >60 years. Each group was further categorized into male (detected and not detected) and female (detected and not detected) group. These groups were analyzed by using openepi software two by two tables to find out odd ratio. Odd ratio is test of association within an outcome and exposure. The odd ratio shows that an outcome will occur offered a specific exposure, compared to the

odds of the outcome occurring in the lack of that exposure.

RESULTS

The COVID-19 Positivity rate in different age groups during 1st wave and 2nd wave from May 2020 to February 2021 data has shown in the Table 1. It is calculated that infection of COVID-19 was highest among July 2020, and November 2020 as shown in graph 1 and graph 2. The male vs female ratio was shown in graph 3 while overall number positive cases are represented in Graph 4.

TABLE: COVID-19 Positivity rate in different age groups from May 2020 to January 2021

Month	Age Groups (year)	Male positive cases	Male Negative cases	Female positive cases	Female Negative cases	Total positive cases
MAY 2020	≤30 years	1963	5655	1032	2725	2995
	31-60 years	4063	9104	1319	2374	5382
	> 60 years	960	1143	447	666	1407
JUNE 2020	≤30 years	4138	12583	2192	5669	6330
	31-60 years	9224	19879	3674	6459	12898
	> 60 years	2303	2948	1324	1698	3627
JULY 2020	≤30 years	544	4002	369	2402	913
	31-60 years	1582	7155	693	2655	2275
	> 60 years	419	1210	233	711	652
AUGUST 2020	≤30 years	146	3404	95	1801	245

	31-60 years	342	5058	178	1892	520
	> 60 years	109	778	65	462	174
	≤30 years	171	5011	130	2776	301
SEPTEMBER 2020	31-60 years	408	4616	230	2072	638
	> 60 years	113	814	88	512	201
	≤30 years	397	4946	303	2709	700
OCTOBER 2020	31-60 years	868	6222	532	2480	1400
	> 60 years	295	969	178	662	473
	≤30 years	1317	6013	992	3700	2309
NOVEMBER 2020	31-60 years	2941	8720	1670	3965	4611
	> 60 years	1020	1746	613	1161	1633
	≤30 years	983	5947	748	3745	1731
DECEMBER 2020	31-60 years	2386	9940	1394	4724	3780
	> 60 years	862	2168	529	1469	1391
	≤30 years	552	4517	389	2508	941
JANUARY 2021	31-60 years	1277	6965	893	3537	2170
	> 60 years	562	1597	394	1195	956
	≤30 years	470	3603	446	2676	916
FEBRUARY 2021	31-60 years	1159	5495	784	2727	1943
	> 60 years	429	1071	346	993	775

GRAPH ONE: Comparison of Detected Patients of different age categories during 1st wave of COVID-19

GRAPH TWO: Comparison of Detected Patients of different age categories during 2nd wave of COVID-19

GRAPH THREE: Comparison of Male Vs Female Detected Patients during 1st and 2nd wave of COVID-19

GRAPH 4: Overall Comparison of Total Detected Patients during 1st and 2nd wave of COVID-19

DISCUSSION

Based on published data, SARS (CoV-2) virus looks to infect children in low frequently and low in severely compared to adults. Related to the study published from so many regions, the percentage of children

among COVID-19 infected patients was in ratio quite low (2.1 - 2.4% proportion in China, 1.3% proportion in Italy, 2.8% proportion in Australia, and 7.0% proportion in Korea)Jo *et al.* 2020).

One of the present issues in the presence of virus COVID-19 pandemic season crisis is to detect the effects and occurrence of the 2nd wave on public health to prepare appropriate approach to minimize negative effects in this society. The current study here detects 1st and 2nd wave of corona virus COVID-19 pandemic season in Italy. Results shows that the 1st wave of COVID-19 virus pandemic season in Italy had a more negative effects on people health duration from February to month May 2020 that shows declined level with the arriving of summer season and as well as with the health related policy and SOPs of lockdown and quarantine, rather than, 2nd wave of the pandemic COVID-19, from month October 2020, has increasing number of confirmed COVID cases but number of admitted to ICUs is below higher number and total number of deaths have a much lower level than 1st wave (Coccia 2020). In my research work positivity rate of infected persons with COVID-19 in May, June, July, August and September of 1st wave has a higher ratio of positivity as compared to October, November, December, January and February of 2nd wave of COVID-19. There may be awareness about COVID-19 mode of transmission, health care seeking behavior and social distancing as well as other factor is immunity system. Total positive cases were less in May month it increases with time to time and transmitted to other people increased in June month it was on its peak, it decreased with a smaller number of positivity rate reported in July and also decreased in August. While in September there were increased numbers of COVID-19 positivity rate as compared to August month. On the other hand, it increased in October as well as in November month also while in December month positivity rate reported cases comes in decline phase. It was continuously decreased in December and it further decreased in January as well as in February month reported cases.

Data on COVID-19 in Germany say that age group 15-34 years prevalence more with time to other age group 35-49 years old and children age group 10-14 years. We determine related changes occurred in the incidence of COVID-19 cases in other age groups in state Germany applying positive data on detected which is reported COVID-19 confirmed cases (Goldstein and Lipsitch 2020). In this research work in every month there were probability of COVID-19 positivity rate varies in every age groups in males and females in different months. But there was higher rate of positivity in 31-60 years age group increased incidence compared with other age group ≤ 30 years and other >60 years. There may be many relative reasons for this

age group higher positivity rate occurred in 1st wave of COVID-19 pandemic and 2nd wave of COVID-19 pandemic relatively. There may be awareness about COVID-19 mode of transmission, health care seeking behavior and social distancing as well as other factor is immunity system. Recommends that there were those age groups may be expected to have the extensive role in attaining the currently occurred SARS-CoV-2 pandemic season however, the age group distribution of COVID-19 detected cases reported in South Korea (Goldstein and Lipsitch 2020).

In those sensational analyses, there was a more increase in RR (relative risk) for the group 15-24 year age, and the RR evaluate in the 25-34 year age group persisted higher than in age groups 35-49 year and age group 10-14 years (Peak *et al.*).

In this research by applying odd ratio find that in this age group COVID-19 probability is more in males having age ≤ 30 years than in females having age ≤ 30 years but there is not any association between male and female to be infected with COVID-19. In this age group COVID-19 probability is more in males having age 31-60 years than in females having age 31-60 years but there is not any association between male and female to be infected with COVID-19. In this age group COVID-19 probability is more in males having age > 60 years than in females having age > 60 years but there is association between male and female to be infected with COVID-19. In whole time period of COVID-19 pandemic season May to November which include 1st wave of COVID-19 and 2nd wave of COVID-19, in every month age group >60 years is significant there is association between male and female to be infected with COVID-19. While other age groups ≤ 30 years and age 31-60 years there is not any association between male and female to be infected with COVID-19. In every group male infectivity ratio is more in number than in females.

CONCLUSION

Positivity rate of infected persons with COVID-19 in month May, June, July, August and September of 1st wave has a higher ratio of positive reported cases as compared to October, November, December, January and February of 2nd wave of COVID-19. Total positive cases were less in May month, it increases with time and increased in June month it was peak of COVID-19 positivity and it again decreased with a smaller number of positivity rate reported in July and further decreased in August month. While in September month it increased numbers of COVID-19 positivity rate. Furthermore, it was increased in October as well

as higher number of positive cases in November month it was peak of 2nd wave. In December positivity rate decreased and in January and February month COVID-19 positive reported cases also decreased.

RECOMMENDATION

Positivity rate is higher in 31–60-year age group there is more precautions and awareness required. Now there is an urgent need for the vaccination of very safe and effective vaccine to reduce this highly infectious disease as COVID-19 vaccine in process currently in Pakistan.

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